

AN EVALUATION OF CUSTOMER SATISFACTION WITH AMAZON IN HYDERABAD

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ABSTRACT

The significance of this study aims towards the satisfaction level received by a shopper performing through Amazon. Customers support is typically viewed because the power force of the connection between the perspective of individual's relative and repeat help. Customer loyalty is one foremost over used phrases in business today. Client should purchase something from on-line like as books, household's product, ornaments, hardware and code etc. Moreover, in only few decade the net has become additional standard to Adult and youngsters shopper as a result of the net offers additional and additional benefits. There square measure several different sites apart from amazon however a number of the factors distinguish Amazon from its competitors like giant sort of quality merchandise. This paper is a shot to analyse client satisfaction level of Amazon.

KEYWORDS: Satisfaction level, customers, competitors.

I.INTRODUCTION

The aim of every business to increase sales by finding out the factors that drive consumers buying decisions. Satisfaction is that the method of choosing, organizing, and decoding or attaching aspiring to events happening in setting. Over the past few years, online looking has redoubled the proportion of on-line buyer's in India. . Internet became a lot of powerful and basic tool for each person's want and therefore the means folks work. By desegregation varied on-line info management tools victimisation net, varied innovative corporations have discovered systems for taking customer orders, facilitate creating of payments, customer service, assortment of promoting knowledge , and on-line feedback severally. Customer always

seeks a products which can offer functional, symbolic, emotional, and situational benefits to them primary to satisfaction of their needs and wants, thus we called a wings of successful brand is great product or service forward with planning and a great deal of strategy.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

Oliva, Oliver & MacMillan (2018), primarily planned the idea of “expectation inconformity”, that is, once the goods' sensible scenario is on the far side their expectation the purchasers can feel glad. However, contemporarily come back up there with the product and repair quality also will directly have an effect on the customers' Satisfaction. The study finds that with the advantages of net and inclusion value reductions ways in operations, one will enhance its competitive position in method, structure and relationship terms. The paper additionally discusses the advantages of e-commerce and therefore the uncertainty of the long run e-commerce business. Naveen Prasadula known the most factors influencing the customer perception of the e-service quality on-line shopping: website style (degree of users friendliness), dependability (reliability and security), responsiveness (responsiveness and helpfulness), trust (trust and mechanisms provided by a website), and personalization (differentiating services to satisfy specific individual needs).

Wilson, Zeithaml, Bitner & Gremler's (2008) view, the selling isn't just like the ancient selling any longer. It's was relationship selling currently which suggests customers additionally involve the full business methods. UN agency ought to take their customers into thought and understand what customers very wants.

III. OBJECTIVES:

- To study the socio economic background of respondents.
- To analyse the satisfaction level of shopping in amazon.
- To establish what form of the merchandise area unit sold in amazon.
- To conclude the issues featured by the shoppers within the online searching from amazon.
- To live the satisfaction of customers towards exchange/refund policy.

IV. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY:

- The study is completed solely with the preference of buyers towards Amazon.
- Respondent's opinion might not be free from basis.

- The sample size was restricted to 120 respondents.
- The study is confined to Hyderabad district solely.
- The study is predicated upon the patron behavior of on-line looking.
- The data collected for the analysis is totally on primary data given by the respondents.

V. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

Research comprise process and redefining, formation hypothesis or advised resolution, collection, organizing and evaluating knowledge, creating detection and reaching conclusion and eventually rigorously testing the conclusion to see either they work the formatted hypothesis.

RESEARCH DESIGN:

Exploratory research design has been utilized in this study.

SOURCES OF DATA:

PRIMARY DATA:

The primary data for this study is collected from respondents through structured form.

SECONDARY DATA:

The secondary data for this study is collected from totally different sources such Journals, magazines and websites.

SAMPLE SIZE:

The sample size is 120 is taken for this study.

SAMPLING DESIGN:

This sampling used for the study is convenience sampling method.

METHODS OF DATA COLLECTING:

The info needed for this study were collected from the choosen sample. The strategy used for knowledge assortment could be a structured form.

TOOLS:

The analytical tools used square measure largely graphical in nature which include,

- Presentation tool - charts.
- Analytical tool - proportion analysis.

VI. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION:

This chapter deals with analysis and interpretation of data. The data is collected through structured questionnaire. The data is analysed presented in the form the table with necessary interpretation.

The information analysed and taken on the idea of

A. Socio economic standing of respondents.

- Gender
- Age
- Occupation
- Monthly financial gain

B. Extent to the study on customer satisfaction towards Amazon.

TABLE 1: REPRESENTING THE GENDER OF RESPONDENTS

SL NO	GENDER	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
1	Male	41	25%
2	Female	59	75%
Total		100	100%

Sources: Primary data

INTERPRETATION:

In the above table shows that 25% respondents are under the male category, 75% respondent are under the female category.

Majority (75%) of the respondents are under the female category.

CHART 1: REPRESENTING THE GENDER OF THE RESPONDENTS

TABLE 2: REPRESENTING THE OCCUPATION OF RESPONDENTS

SL NO	OCCUPATION	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
1	Student	64	80%
2	Business	14	7%
3	professional	18	10%
4	others	4	3%
TOTAL		100	100%

Sources: Primary data

INTERPRETATION:

In the above table shows that 80% respondent are under the category of student, 7% of respondent are under the category of business, 10% of respondent are under the category of professional, 3% of respondent are under the category of others.

Majority (80%) of the respondents are under the category of Student.

CHART: 2 REPRESENTING THE OCCUPATION OF RESPONDENTS

TABLE 3: REPRESENTING THE INCOME OF RESPONDENTS

SL NO	INCOME	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
1	Less than 20000	9	5%
2	20000 – 50000	15	7%
3	50000 - 100000	22	10%
4	Above 100000	6	3%
5	No Income	48	75%
TOTAL		100	100%

Sources: Primary data

INTERPRETATION:

In the above table shows that 5 % of respondent are earning under the category of less than 20000 , 7 % of respondent are earning under the category of 20000-50000, 10 % of respondent are earning under the category of 50000-100000, 3% of respondent are earning under the category of above 1 lakh, 75% of respondent are under the category No income.

Majority (75%) of the respondents are earning under the category of no income.

CHART 3: REPRESENTING THE INCOME OF RESPONDENTS

TABLE 4: REPRESENTING THAT WHY CHOOSING THE AMAZON OF RESPONDENTS:

SL NO	WHY AMAZON	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
1	Provide good services	36	65%
2	Lower prices	20	10%
3	Pay safety	15	7%
4	Convenient	24	15%
5	Others	5	3%
TOTAL		100	100%

Sources: Primary data

INTERPRETATION:

In the above table shows that 65 % of respondent are under the category of provide good services , 10 % of respondent are under the category of lower prices, 7 % of respondent are under the category of pay safety, 15% of respondent are under the category of convenient, 3% of respondent are under the category others.

Majority (65%) of the respondents are under the category of others.

CHART 4: REPRESENTING THAT WHY CHOOSING THE AMAZON OF RESPONDENTS:

TABLE 5: REPRESENTING THAT SATISFACTION LEVEL USING AMAZON:

SL NO	SATISFACTION LEVEL	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
1	Very satisfied	22	10%
2	satisfied	64	85%
3	Neutral	13	4%
4	Dissatisfied	1	1%
5	Very dissatisfied	0	0%
TOTAL		100	100%

Sources: Primary data

INTERPRETATION:

In the above table shows that 10% respondent are under the category of Very satisfied, 85% respondent are under the category of satisfied, 4% respondent are under the category of neutral, 1% respondent are under the category of Dissatisfied, 0% respondent are under the category of very dissatisfied.

Majority (85%) of the respondents are under the category of satisfied.

CHART 5: REPRESENTING THAT SATISFACTION LEVEL USING AMAZON:

TABLE 6: REPRESENTING THAT KIND OF PRODUCTS PURCHASE MOSTLY:

SL.NO	PRODUCTS	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
1	Clothing, shoes and ornaments	49	78%
2	Home, garden and tools	26	15%
3	Tools and decor	11	2%
4	Others	14	5%
TOTAL		100	100%

Sources: Primary data

INTERPRETATION:

In the above table shows that 78% of respondent are under the category of Clothing, shoes and ornaments, 15% of respondent are under the category of Home, garden and tools, 2% of respondent are under the category of Tools and decor, 5% of respondent are under the category of others.

Majority (78%) of the respondents are under the category of Clothing, shoes and ornaments.

CHART 6: REPRESENTING THAT KIND OF PRODUCTS PURCHASE MOSTLY:

TABLE 7: REPRESENTING THAT KIND OF PROBLEMS DID YOU FACED IN AMAZON:

SI.NO	PROBLEMS FACED	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
1	Bad services	11	4%
2	Bad quality	17	6%
3	Delay delivery	26	22%
4	No problem faced	46	68%
TOTAL		100	100%

Sources: Primary data

INTERPRETATION:

In the above table shows that 4% of respondent are under the category of Bad services, 6% of respondent are under the category of Bad quality, 22% of respondent are under the category of Delay delivery, 68% of respondent are under the category of No problems faced.

Majority (68%) of the respondents are under the category of No problems faced.

CHART 7: REPRESENTING THAT KIND OF PROBLEMS DID YOU FACED IN AMAZON:

TABLE 8: RERESENTING THAT EXCHANGE/REFUND POLICY:

SL.NO	EXCHANGE /REFUND POLICY	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
1	Yes	47	85.5%
2	No	38	11.5%
3	Maybe	15	3%
TOTAL		100	100%

Sources: Primary data

INTERPRETATION:

In the above table shows that 85.5% respondent are under the category of yes , 11.5% respondent are under the category of no , 3% respondents are under the category of may be.

Majority (85.5%) of the respondents are under the category of yes.

CHART 8: REPRESENTING THAT EXCHANGE/REFUND POLICY:

TABLE 9: REPRESENTING THAT LONG USING AMAZON FOR SHOPPING:

SI.NO	LONG USING AMAZON	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
1	Less than 1 year	34	28%
2	1 year – 3 year	40	60%
3	More than 3 year	26	12%
TOTAL		100	100%

Sources: Primary data

INTERPRETATION:

In the above table shows that 28% respondent are under the category of Less than 1 year, 60% respondent are under the category of 1 year -3 year , 12% respondents are under the category of more than 3 year.

Majority (60%) of the respondents are under the category of 1 year – 3 year.

CHART 9: REPRESENTING THAT LONG USING AMAZON FOR SHOPPING:

TABLE 10: REPRESENTING THAT THE TIME SPEND FOR SHOPPING

SI.NO	TIME FOR SPENDING	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
1	Every day	8	5%
2	Monthly once	36	65%
3	2-3 months	28	15%
4	More than 3 months	28	15%
TOTAL		100	100%

Sources: Primary data

INTERPRETATION:

In the above table shows that 5% respondent are under the category of every day, 65% respondent are under the category of monthly once, 15% respondents are under the category of 2-3 months, 15% respondents are under the category of more than 3 months.

Majority (65%) of the respondents are under the category of Monthly once.

CHART 10: REPRESENTING THAT THE TIME SPEND FOR SHOPPING

TABLE 11: REPRESENTING THAT MONEY CAN SPEND FOR SHOPPING

SI.NO	MONEY SPEND	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
1	Under 500	13	15%
2	500-1000	49	60%
3	1000-5000	30	20%
4	Above 5000	8	5%
TOTAL		100	100%

Sources: Primary data

INTERPRETATION:

In the above table shows that 15% of respondent are under the category of under 500, 60% of respondent are under the category of 500-1000, 20% of respondent are under the category of 1000-5000, 5% of respondent are under the category of above 5000.

Majority (60%) of the respondents are under the category of Above 5000.

CHART 11: REPRESENTING THAT MONEY CAN SPEND FOR SHOPPING

TABLE 12: REPRESENTING THAT MODE OF PAYMENT PREFERRED

SI.NO	MODE OF PAYMENT	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
1	Net banking	11	4%
2	Cash on delivery	59	75%
3	Credit or debit cards	28	20%
4	Others	2	1%
TOTAL		100	100%

Sources: Primary data

INTERPRETATION:

In the above table shows that 4% of respondent are under the category of Net banking, 75% of respondent are under the category of cash on delivery, 20% of respondent are under the category of credit or debit cards, 1% of respondent are under the category of others.

Majority (75%) of the respondents are under the category of cash on delivery

CHART 12: REPRESENTING THAT MODE OF PAYMENT PREFERRED

TABLE 13: REPRESENTING THAT SOURCES WHICH MAKE PURCHASES

SI.NO	SOURCES MAKE YOU PURCHASES	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
1	Family and friends	56	70%
2	Transaction security	16	7%
3	advertisement	22	20%
4	Ethics	6	3%
TOTAL		100	100%

Sources: Primary data

INTERPRETATION:

In the above table shows that 70% of respondent are under the category of Family and friends, 7% of respondent are under the category of transaction security, 20% of respondent are under the category of advertisements, 3% of respondent are under the category of ethics.

Majority (70%) of the respondents are under the category of family and friends.

CHART 13: REPRESENTING THAT SOURCES WHICH MAKE PURCHASES

TABLE 14: REPRESENTING THAT RATE PRICES OF PRODUCT OFFERED

Sl.NO	RATE PRICES OFFERED	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
1	Reasonable	46	86.5%
2	Premium price	31	8.5%
3	At a discount	23	5%
TOTAL		100	100%

Sources: Primary data

INTERPRETATION:

In the above table shows that 86.5% of respondent are under the category of Reasonable, 8.5% of respondent are under the category of premium price, 5% of respondent are under the category of At a discount.

Majority (86.5%) of the respondents are under the category of Reasonable.

CHART 14: REPRESENTING THAT RATE PRICES OF PRODUCT OFFERED

TABLE 15: REPRESENTING THAT REASONABLE RETURN AND EXCHANGE POLICY

SI.NO	RETURN AND EXCHANGE POLICY	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
1	Strongly agree	18	10%
2	Agree	53	70%
3	neutral	23	18%
4	disagree	3	1%
5	Strongly disagree	3	1%
TOTAL		100	100%

Sources: Primary data

INTERPRETATION:

In the above table shows that 10% of respondent are under the category of Strongly agree, 70% of respondent are under the category of agree, 18% of respondent are under the category of Neutral, 1% of respondent are under the category of disagree, 1% of respondent are under the category of Strongly disagree.

Majority (70%) of the respondents are under the category of Agree.

CHART 15: REPRESENTING THAT REASONABLE RETURN AND EXCHANGE POLICY

TABLE 16: REPRESENTING THAT RECOMMENDATION AMAZON IS VERY HELPFUL:

SI.NO	RECOMMENDATION IS HELPFULL	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
1	Yes	47	85.5%
2	No	15	5%
3	Maybe	38	10.5%
TOTAL		100	100%

Sources: Primary data

INTERPRETATION:

In the above table shows that 85.5% respondent are under the category of yes , 5% respondent are under the category of no , 10.5% respondents are under the category of may be. **Majority (85.5%) of the respondents are under the category of yes.**

CHART 16: REPRESENTING THAT RECOMMENDATION AMAZON IS VERY HELPFUL:

TABLE 17: REPRESENTING THAT SATISFIED WITH THE SERVICES, PRODUCT AND OTHER COMMODITIES OF AMAZON:

SI.NO	SERVICE, PRODUCT AND COMMODITIES	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
1	Strongly agree	22	15%
2	Agree	55	80%
3	Neutral	19	3%
4	Disagree	4	2%
TOTAL		100	100%

Sources: Primary data

INTERPRETATION:

In the above table shows that 15% of respondent are under the category of Strongly agree, 80% of respondent are under the category of agree, 3% of respondent are under the category of Neutral, 2% of respondent are under the category of disagree.

Majority (80%) of the respondents are under the category of Agree.

CHART 17: REPRESENTING THAT SATISFIED WITH THE SERVICES, PRODUCT AND OTHER COMMODITIES OF AMAZON:

VII. FINDINGS & RESULTS

The major findings of the study and their implications are as follows.

- Mostly the female customers are using amazon, and the majority of people are students. So they are choosing no income.
- It is observed from the above table is statistically significant at five percent level which indicates that there is difference among male and female respondents towards product of amazon.
- Most of the respondents spend time monthly once in a time. And Rs 500 – 1000 to spend money on amazon.
- Most of the respondents usually preferred the mode of payment is cash on delivery.
- The respondents rated the prices of products offered at amazon is reasonable.
- The respondents of sources which make you to purchase the product from amazon is family and friends.
- The respondents of recommendation of amazon is very helpful to the customers.

VIII. CONCLUSION

My literature analysis has discovered that customer satisfaction will be outlined as associate degree overall customers angle towards a service supplier, or associate degree emotional reaction to the distinction between what customers anticipate and what they receive, relating to the fulfilment of some want, goal or need. From the study, customer satisfaction is the

customer's fulfilment response means when a customer happy with the service and the product quality then the customer shows their loyalty towards the company and used to buy the products from that company again which enable more financial benefit in the organizational context. Based upon customer's survey, however Amazon satisfies the customer in the aspect of quality of the products.

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